

Testing the Effectiveness of Gratitude Journaling as a Positive Psychology Intervention

by

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A positive psychology intervention—henceforth PPI—is a broad term encompassing any activity undertaken with the primary aim of promoting one’s wellbeing, the quality of one’s overall positive psychological state (Sin & Lyubomirsky, 2009). According to Seligman, Steen, Park and Peterson (2005), PPIs generally attempt to promote wellbeing by fostering gratitude, introspectively reflecting on one’s positive qualities, and identifying and cultivating one’s strengths. Examples of commonly implemented PPIs include meditation, acts of kindness where individuals are tasked to carry out specific good deeds throughout the PPI, and gratitude interventions such as gratitude journaling (Bolier et al., 2013). It has been found that PPIs can be applied to an array of different settings such as preventing mental illnesses in schools, aiding those who have been severely traumatised by extreme natural disasters, and complementing medication when treating chronic diseases (Vernberg, Hambrick, Cho, Hendrickson, 2016; Chodkiewicz & Boyle, 2017; Ghosh & Deb, 2017).

I implemented gratitude journaling as a PPI to test its effectiveness on my overall wellbeing and to test the validity of the claims of gratitude intervention research. There is a growing body of evidence that practicing gratitude, typically through a gratitude journal, has the capacity to promote wellbeing via specific mechanisms such as catalysing the reciprocity of gratitude within relationships, reinforcing recall of positive events, and reducing stress levels (Carter et al., 2016; Emmons & McCullough, 2003; Caleon et al., 2017). In addition, meta-analyses of gratitude intervention research literature found that while any definitive image of the effectiveness of gratitude interventions remains hazy, the current literature indicates that gratitude interventions have a low to moderate efficacy in promoting positive emotions (Davis et al., 2016; Dickens, 2017). The following discussion outlines the method by which gratitude journaling was tested as a PPI, summarises the results obtained, and analyses how the research literature on gratitude and other prominent positive psychology theories relate to the results of the subjective wellbeing measures used in the PPI.

The Procedure of Gratitude Journaling

In order to effectively implement gratitude journaling as a PPI, a standard routine was followed during the pre-test (1 week before PPI), the 5-day intervention (during which gratitude journaling was done daily), and the post-test (1 week after PPI). 10 minutes was spent gratitude journaling wherein the first 5 minutes was spent reflecting on the day (i.e. using memory and by scanning through phone photos and messages) to pick out 3-5 events that I was most grateful for; the last 5 minutes was spent articulating those events in a OneNote notebook and filling up the questionnaires for the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) and the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS). The intervention was routinely implemented at around 8 P.M. in the library before heading home.

Examples of gratitude journal entries during the intervention include:

- Had lunch with Jen (been waiting a week for it!) and she's willing to hang out again. I'm very excited about the prospect of a meaningful friendship.
- Typed code for the graph for WMP Assignment 2 in Rstudio. I never thought I'd ever use R for anything useful again so I'm thankful that all those hours coding benefitted me.

Results Obtained and a Brief Analysis of Key Trends

The graph above shows an upward trend for both the PANAS Positive Affect and the SWLS scores, although there was a slight drop from the end of the intervention to the post-test for both scores. The PANAS Negative Affect scores show a steady downward trend with the score maintaining constant post-intervention. It can be deduced that overall wellbeing increased as PANAS Negative Affect decreased over time and PANAS Positive Affect and SWLS scores increased markedly over time.

The increase in both PANAS Positive Affect and SWLS can likely be attributed to an increased sense of awareness of events that I can be grateful for throughout the day. Gratitude journaling as a PPI made me actively try to find and remember events that I can be grateful for as each day unfolded; this increased my wellbeing as my entire view of the world started shifting

to become a lens through which feelings of gratitude were more likely to be elicited. The slight drop in PANAS Positive Affect and SWLS post-intervention is most likely present because I discontinued the PPI after the 5 days. The post-test score is still higher than my pre-test score because throughout the intervention the gratitude journal inspired me to practice acts of gratitude such as making a simple care package for a stressed friend and inviting people out for coffee; the following week after the intervention, these people reciprocated with similar acts and this has buffered any major decrease in wellbeing.

Concordance of Results and Experience with PPI Research Literature

The increase in my wellbeing and the trends observed caused by the gratitude journal as a PPI is highly concordant with findings in multiple studies. Firstly, the increase in my wellbeing caused by using a gratitude journal only adds on to the ever-growing evidence that gratitude journals are effective as a PPI (Seligman et al. 2005; Mongrain & Anselmo-Matthews 2012; Carter et al., 2016). Moreover, in the results of my PPI, SWLS and PANAS Positive Affect had a marked increase over the 5 days as compared to the lesser extent to which PANAS Negative Affect decreased. This is supported by a study conducted by Mongrain and Anselmo-Matthews (2012) which demonstrates that PPIs are more effective at increasing positive affect compared to decreasing negative affect. Furthermore, the reason as to why my post-intervention score did not increase can be explained by Seligman et al. (2005) who argue that long-term effectiveness of a PPI is dependent on whether individuals continue to utilise the PPI even after the period in which they were supposed to carry out has passed.

Other studies support my experience with gratitude journaling and the mechanisms by which it promoted my wellbeing. For instance, Carter et al. (2016) state that gratitude journals reinforces and promotes one's skill of recalling positive events and, in turn, increases

wellbeing. In addition, Emmons and McCullough (2003) claim that individuals who use gratitude journals were more likely to be spurred to practice acts of gratitude and kindness and thus strengthen their social ties. Caleon et al. (2017) builds on this notion by stating that gratitude drives a cycle of reciprocity in relationships wherein acts of gratitude encourage the receiver of the act to return the favour and for the benefactor to further engage in acts of gratitude. This notion of reciprocity of gratitude in relationships catalysed by gratitude is exactly what I experienced during the PPI. Lastly, on a more specific note, just like the example regarding the RStudio code above, I often wrote about how grateful I was for the knowledge that I was gaining at university. On this, Wilson (2016) maintains that students who actively attempt to be grateful towards their studies are more likely to have reduced stress levels and persevere when struggling to grasp difficult concepts. I experienced this as the gratitude journal allowed me view studying less as a chore by reminding me how much of an invaluable opportunity learning is; this led to a noticeable increase in focus and positive feelings during my study time during the PPI.

The results obtained in the PPI are also related to several prominent positive psychology theories such as optimism bias and the broaden-and-build theory. According to Sharot (2011), having an optimism bias, the belief that future events will have positive outcomes regardless of known statistical probabilities, leads to optimal human functioning by means of reducing stress levels and increasing productivity at work. In parallel, gratitude journaling, through reinforcing one's skill of recalling positive events (Carter et al., 2016), creates a mindset, as it did in me during my experience, that future events will also contain positive events. This boosts human functioning by having a greater sense of control of one's situation despite the actual rockiness of reality. Moreover, the broaden-and-build theory, the idea that positive emotions broaden the scope of an individual's actions by encouraging him or her to practice acts that promote wellbeing and, consequently, build on what Fredrickson (2004) refers to as the

individual's "physical, intellectual, social, and psychological resources. (p.1367)" This is related directly to my experience as during my PPI, positive feelings of gratitude encouraged me to practice acts of kindness and to study more efficiently and with less stress. As a result, my resources—in particular, my relationships and the output of my study time—flourished.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The results obtained are significant in that they show trends that correspond directly to several key findings in the gratitude intervention literature and indicate that gratitude journaling as a PPI is effective at promoting wellbeing. Overall, as it was qualitatively presented in the graph above, it can be conclusively stated that the PPI had a moderate effect on improving my wellbeing. Based on the correspondence between my experience and the extant gratitude intervention research literature, it was maintained that gratitude journaling increased my wellbeing through the betterment of my relationships with others, helping me more effectively remember positive experiences, and reducing my stress levels and elevating my focus when studying. To improve gratitude journaling as a PPI, I suggest that the intervention should last much longer to instil deeper change, that other measures of subjective wellbeing are used, and that the effectiveness of pairing gratitude journaling with other complementary PPIs such as mindfulness should also be tested.

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